

EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE JOINT GAP CLOSURE WITH INSTALLATION OF DIFFERENT FASTENER SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

An evaluation of mechanically fastened composite joints assembled with gaps between the faying surfaces has been completed. The purpose of the evaluation was to compare the amount of damage and/or residual gap caused by clamp-up forces during the installation of three types of 1/4" diameter fastener systems installed in three different specimen configurations. The configurations simulated aircraft structural arrangements that have experienced problems during fastener installations in the past. Post-assembly ultrasonic inspections were performed on all specimens to specifically identify and record the presence of delamination and/or residual gap after fastener installation. Lockbolt fasteners showed no damage to acceptable baseline gap locations and proved to be the most consistent at closing the acceptable baseline gaps.

1. BACKGROUND

Huck International has performed an extensive number of tests that have examined the use of the titanium lockbolts in composite materials. This test was designed to evaluate the relative amount of delamination and/or residual gap caused by the clamp forces of three different fastener systems installed into three different simulated gap-prone composite aircraft structure assemblies.

In the recent past, low clamp fasteners have been used to avoid assembly delamination of laminated composite joints with gaps between the faying surfaces. Testing at the Huck Technical Center has shown that in some cases low clamp fasteners *will not* pull the plates completely together leaving a residual gap. The presence of residual gap has proven to decrease static and dynamic joint performance dramatically. Testing has also shown that the performance loss due to residual gap is much more severe than that of localized delamination due to fastener installation.

To determine the amount of delamination **and** check for the presence of residual gap in a fastened joint, non-destructive testing was used. Delamination can be determined by careful disassembly and sectioning of the structure. Residual gap, however, can only be identified by leaving the assembly intact with fasteners installed.

The detection of air gaps between two faying surfaces (residual gap) of a fastened joint is :

difficult task but can be achieved via enhanced ultrasonic C-scan through transmission equipment and the use of sealed specimens. The specimens must be sealed to prevent any water entering into the residual gap. If water were present between the faying surfaces (in the residual gap), sound would be transmitted through the water filled gap to the receiver with no loss of the signal and no detection of the gap. With only air present in the gap all sound energy is reflected from the specimen air gap interface resulting in no transmission through the fastened joint. The original signal is not detected by the receiver resulting in detection of the air gap on the C-scan trace. The detection of the transition from air gap to faying surface contact can only be achieved by supplying a high energy ultrasonic sound wave to the fastened joint. Special techniques were developed and used for this test to accurately detect residual gaps.

3. TEST PLAN

Two primary specimen configurations were evaluated for allowable gap testing. Figures 1 and 2 show the improper wing skin to substructure (shimmed assembly) specimen and substructure to substructure specimen (angle pull-up) configurations. A third type of specimen configuration represented the attachment of wing skins to spars at sealant groove locations. Huck International does not recommend the use of lockbolts in this type of laminated composite joint. However, the Huck Technical Center did perform the sealant groove installation tests with all the fastener types, except lockbolts, to provide visibility on the effect this type of gap condition has on the fasteners of concern. Figure 3 is the sealant groove test configuration.

The shimmed and angle pull-up assembly designs incorporated adjustable gap dimensions while the sealant groove assembly had a fixed gap. The shimmed assembly design used a tapered orientation of shims (see figure 1) that created a constant decrease in the gap width. The shim thickness was also variable. Shim thicknesses used were .005", .007", .009", .012" and .015". The angle pull-up assembly was designed to vary the separation between the aluminum and composite angle upright surfaces (see figure 2). The angle pull-up gap separations used were .005", .010", .015", .020" and .030". The sealant groove assembly fixed gap measured .500" by .065" deep.

All laminates were quasi-isotropic layups with 25% 0° plies, 50% 45° plies and 25% 90° plies. The shimmed assembly and seal groove assembly composite plates (Figure 1) were made of AS4/3501-6 unidirectional tape. The substructure composite angles (Figure 2) were fabricated with 3K 12X12 plain weave AS4/3501-6 fabric. One hundred-degree countersunk fasteners were installed in the shimmed and seal groove assemblies (Figures 1 and 3) Protruding head fasteners were installed in the angle pull-up assemblies (Figure 2) with the head against the aluminum angle. The shimmed assembly tests had one specimen which used protruding head fasteners instead of countersunk fasteners. Tables 1, 2 and 3 specify the test matrices and the materials used for each assembly.

The installation of the three fastener systems was accomplished using standard installation tools as follows:

- Hi-Lok fastener installation tool
 - Ingersol Rand model 5LNU1 30° angle ratchet type nut runner
 - Air line pressure 90 psi
- HUCKCOMP "C" Lockbolt installation tool
 - Pneudraulic 225 installation tool
 - Air line pressure 90 psi
 - 99-1174 nose assembly
- Torq-Set/Hex Bolts installed with

Figure 1 Shimmed Assembly Configuration

Figure 2 Angle Pull-up Configuration

Figure 3 Sealant Groove Configuration

Table 1. Shimmed Assembly Test Matrix

Fastener Type	Collar/Nut Type	Fastener Description	Plate Thickness	Shim Thickness
HL13-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015
HL10-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, PROT	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015
HL13-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.132"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015
HL13-8-07	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.185"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015
NAS1580C4T5	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
NAS6704U5	MS21076	HEXBOLT PROT	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
NAS1580C4T5	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.132"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
NAS1580C4T6	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.185"	.005, .007, .009, .012 *
LGPL8SC-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT 100° CS	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
LGPL9SP-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT PROT	.090"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
LGPL8SC-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT 100° CS	.132"	.005, .007, .009, .012, .015 *
LGPL8SC-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT 100° CS	.185"	.005, .007, .009, .012 *

* Tested shim thicknesses were determined by the Hi-Lok (baseline) test results. Actual tested shim thicknesses are shown.

Table 2. Angle Pull-up Assembly Test Matrix

Fastener Type	Collar/Nut Type	Fastener Description	Plate Thickness	Gap Thickness
HL10-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, PROT	.088"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030
HL10-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, PROT	.132"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030
HL10-8-07	HL70-8	HI-LOK, PROT	.176"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030
NAS6704U5	MS21076	HEXBOLT,PROT	.088"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **
NAS6704U5	MS21076	HEXBOLT,PROT	.132"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **
NAS6704U5	MS21076	HEXBOLT,PROT	.176"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **
LGPL9SP-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT PROT	.088"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **
LGPL9SP-V08-C06	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT PROT	.132"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **
LGPL9SP-V08-C07	SLFC-MV08	LOCKBOLT PROT	.176"	.005, .010, .015, .020, .030 **

** Tested gap thicknesses were determined by the Hi-Lok (baseline) test results. Actual tested gap thicknesses are shown.

Table 3. Sealant Groove Assembly Test Matrix

Fastener Type	Collar/Nut Type	Fastener Description	Plate Thickness	Groove Depth
HL10-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.088"	.065"
HL10-8-06	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.132"	.065"
HL10-8-07	HL70-8	HI-LOK, 100°CS	.176"	.065"
NAS6704U5	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.088"	.065"
NAS6704U5	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.132"	.065"
NAS6704U5	MS21076	Torq-Set 100°CS	.176"	.065"

4. TEST PROCEDURE

The majority of the testing for this study was performed by an independent test lab specializing in non-destructive testing. The coupon fabrication was also performed by an outside source while the assembly of the coupons was accomplished by the Huck Technical Center.

The through transmission configuration used high energy ultrasonic waves supplied via a flat focus type 2.25 MHz transducer. An Infometrics-Testpro data acquisition system was used to store the scanned information. Figure 4 is a sketch of the through transmission setup used to identify residual gaps. The detection of delamination was accomplished using a C-scan pulse echo configuration as drawn in figure 5. A 15 MHz PVDF transducer was used at a 2" focus. Time-of-flight data was gathered with the delamination identification threshold set at -10 db.

The testing and assembly for all three configurations was performed as follows;

- Fabricate composite and aluminum pieces as match sets
- Pre-assembly C-scan inspect for machining delaminations
- Assemble baseline coupons
 - All configurations, shim thicknesses and fastener locations were installed with the baseline fasteners. (Fasteners were installed in the Shimmed Assembly starting from the widest gap to the narrowest.)
- Seal baseline configurations with silicone RTV & 3 coats of clear acrylic paint
- C-scan baseline configurations and identify the unsatisfactory hole locations.
 - Unsatisfactory hole locations are defined as those locations that reveal delaminations and/or residual gap after the installation of the baseline fasteners.
- Mark unsatisfactory hole locations on coupon assemblies designated for lockbolt and bolt/nut plate fasteners.
 - Unsatisfactory hole locations **will not** have the non-baseline fasteners installed in them.
- Install lockbolt and bolt/nut plate fasteners in *satisfactory* hole locations
- Water tight seal test coupons
- C-scan test coupons for residual gap and delamination

Figure 4 Through Transmission Setup

Figure 5 C-scan Pulse Echo Setup

5. RESULTS

The results of this evaluation are dependent on the clamp forces of the fasteners installed in each configuration. Table 4 lists the results of fastener clamp tests run on the specific fasteners used for this evaluation. The clamp load tests for the permanent threaded and lockbolt fasteners were accomplished using the Huck 1820 Fastener Tester. The bolt/nut plate loads were determined by applying a torque to a fastener installed in a piezoelectric load cell. Figure 6 is a plot of the torque-clamp load relationship found by testing. A torque value of 70 inch-lbs was used to install the Torq-Set/ nut plate fasteners. Boeing specification BAC 5009 was followed to define the torque value. (BAC 5009 requires 50-75 inch-lbs be used on lubricated bolts with nut plates.)

Table 4 Clamp Force Results

Permanent Threaded (Baseline)Fastener Clamp Tests	
Test Number	Clamp Load (Lbs)
1	2145
2	1680
3	1291
4	1424
5	1832
Average	1674
Standard Deviation	337
Lockbolt Clamp Tests	
1	2930
2	2989
3	3055
4	3100
5	3000
Average	3015
Standard Deviation	65
Bolt/Nut plate (see figure 6)	
Torque	Clamp
70 inch pounds (Per Boeing Specification BAC 5009)	1198

Figure 6 Torq-Set Clamp Load vs Applied Torque

5.3 Shimmed Assembly Results

Tables 5 and 6 are summaries of the damage and/or residual gap for the Shimmed Assemblies installed with the **baseline** permanent threaded fasteners. The results of the baseline installations determined the **unsatisfactory** holes for which the lockbolt and bolt/nut plate fasteners **would not** be installed into. The shaded portions of the table are the unsatisfactory holes. The hole numbering for the Shimmed Assembly started with hole number 1 at the narrowest gap and hole number ten at the widest gap. The type of damage is identified within each shaded box.

Lockbolt results showed **no damage** to the acceptable baseline gap locations. Lockbolts also proved to be very consistent at closing all "acceptable" gaps. The bolt/nut plate recommended torque values were too low to pull out any of the "acceptable" gaps.

5.4 Angle Pull-up Assembly Results

The Angle Pull-up configuration was susceptible to damage in two general areas, the upright leg and the corner. All Angle Pull-up coupons were 100% ultrasonically inspected.

The Angle Pull-up results revealed the cloth AS4/3501-6 material to be tolerant of relatively large gaps. All fasteners pulled out gaps up to .030" without damage to the composite angles. There were also no signs of gross residual gaps.

5.5 Sealant Groove Assembly Results

Severe delamination was found in the .090 thick plates with both the permanent threaded and bolt/nut plate fasteners (Lockbolts not recommended and not used for this assembly). The .090" plates did have a knife edge condition after the 100° countersink was machined. The .132" thick plate was delaminated by the permanent threaded fastener. The .176" laminate was not delaminated by the fasteners, however, residual gap was identified.

Table 5. Shimmed Assembly Test Results Summary

DELAM = Delamination RG = Residual Gap : OK = No Damage		Baseline Fasteners Installed in .090 Thick Composite Shimmed Assembly Plate				
		Shim Height (inches)				
Hole #	Gap Width (in)	0.005	0.007	0.009	0.012	0.015
1	0.371	OK	OK	OK	DELAM	DELAM
2	0.398	OK	OK	OK	DELAM	DELAM
3	0.424	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
4	0.451	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
5	0.478	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
6	0.504	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
7	0.531	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
8	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
9	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
10	0.611	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK

Table 6. Shimmed Assembly Results Summary, continued

DELAM = Delamination RG = Residual Gap : OK = No Damage		Baseline Fasteners Installed in .132" Thick Composite Shimmed Assembly Plate				
		Shim Height (inches)				
Hole #	Gap Width (in)	0.005	0.007	0.009	0.012	0.015
1	0.371	OK	OK	DELAM	DELAM & RG	DELAM
2	0.398	OK	OK	OK	DELAM & RG	DELAM
3	0.424	OK	OK	OK	RG	DELAM & RG
4	0.451	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG
5	0.478	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG
6	0.504	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
7	0.531	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
8	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
9	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
10	0.611	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK

DELAM = Delamination RG = Residual Gap : OK = No Damage		Baseline Fasteners Installed in .190" Thick Composite Shimmed Assembly Plate				
		Shim Height (inches)				
Hole #	Gap Width (in)	0.005	0.007	0.009	0.012	0.015
1	0.371	OK	RG	RG	RG	RG
2	0.398	OK	RG	RG	RG	RG
3	0.424	OK	OK	RG	RG	RG
4	0.451	OK	OK	OK	RG	RG
5	0.478	OK	OK	OK	RG	RG
6	0.504	OK	OK	OK	RG	RG
7	0.531	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG
8	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG
9	0.558	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG
10	0.611	OK	OK	OK	OK	RG

6. COMMENTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The Shimmed Assembly configuration proved to be very effective and efficient in supplying a considerable amount of useful data. The Angle Pull-up configuration did not demonstrate the expected usefulness desired. The .030" maximum gap thickness was too small to invoke damage to the AS4/3501-6 cloth laminate angle. A larger maximum gap thickness should prove more effective but possibly unrealistic relative to the actual use of the material in a production environment. The Sealant Groove slot dimensions and plate combinations are unacceptable for unidirectional AS4/3501-6 quasi-isotropic plate. Further study should be performed to determine the possibility of a better sealant groove design. The effect on static and fatigue performance of the residual gap caused by a sealant groove should also be investigated.

The following conclusions can be made from the results of this test:

- 1) Lockbolts are capable of being installed into the same "good" holes that are used by the permanent threaded fasteners without delamination and/or residual gap.
- 2) Lockbolts close "safe" gaps with greater consistency than the permanent threaded and bolt/nut plate fasteners.
- 3) The composite angles made of 3501-6/AS4 cloth material are tolerant of large gaps.
- 4) The sealant groove assembly results indicate a considerable delamination *intolerance* to fastener installations.